

STUDIES IN CARBOHYDRATES. PART III*. INVESTIGATION OF MODAL GUM (*LANNEA GRANDIS*)

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Lannea grandis (N. O. Anacardiaceae), commonly known as Modal gum, is found to be a polyuronide, composed of galactose, arabinose and a methyluronic acid in the proportion 5:1:1. The methyluronic acid is shown to be 4-methylglucuronic acid. The methoxyl content and the uronic anhydride content of the gum indicate that the gum contains only one uronic acid, viz. 4-methylglucuronic acid.

Lannea grandis (N. O. Anacardiaceae), commonly known as Modal or Shemat, is a big tree found in deciduous forests of India. Modal gum occurs in the form of tears on the bark of this tree and is initially white in colour, changing to brown afterwards. The gum is used in textile printing and medicinally in asthma and rheumatism. However, practically nothing is known about its composition.

The gum swells in water and dissolves in it on keeping. It is easily soluble in sodium hydroxide. A preliminary purification of the gum was carried out by preparing its aqueous solution and adding it to alcohol, when it was obtained as a white powder (ash, 5.1%). The gum containing 0.64% ash was obtained by treating the gum solution with acidified alcohol. The ash content could not be reduced further by repeating the process.

The purified gum is an acid polysaccharide (equiv. 1245 ca.) and is free from nitrogen, sulphur and acetyl group. However, methoxyl group was found to be present in the gum (OMe, 2.38%). It gave positive tests for pentosans and galactan and negative tests for ketoses and methylpentoses. On hydrolysis with 10% sulphuric acid it afforded galactose, arabinose and aldobionic acid. Arabinose and galactose were obtained in the crystalline form from the hydrolysate and were characterised by preparing their functional derivatives.

The uronic acid could not be isolated because of the resistive nature of the aldobionic acid. Drastic hydrolysis of the aldobionic acid furnished galactose only by the decomposition of the uronic acid. The uronic acid could not be identified by simultaneous hydrolysis and oxidation of the gum by HBr and Br₂ according to the method of Goebel and Heidelberger (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1927, 73, 613). It was finally proved to be 4-methylglucuronic acid by isolating the aldobionic acid and subjecting it to methanolysis according to White (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 367). The identity of the acid was proved by its different derivatives and their physical constants.

The quantitative analysis of the gum gave ash, 0.64%; pentosan, 12.31%; 4-methylglucuronic acid anhydride, 16.32%; galactan, 71.47% (by difference). No other sugar was detected. The results indicate the proportion of galactan, pentosan and methyluronic acid anhydride as 5:1:1 respectively.

*The first two papers in this series were published in this *Journal* (1954, 31, 939, 943).

The methoxyl content of the gum and the uronic acid anhydride content indicate that there should be only one uronic acid, viz., 4-methylglucuronic acid. Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2646) on the other hand found both glucuronic and 4-methylglucuronic acid in mesquite gum.

EXPERIMENTAL

The crude gum, supplied by the Forest Department of Bombay State, was a mixture of brown and white gum tears. These, when dissolved in water and precipitated with alcohol, afforded a white powder (ash, 5.1%). The hand-picked, faintly white or colorless gum tears (60 g.) were powdered, suspended in water (200 c. c.) and sodium hydroxide (25 c. c. of 20%) was gradually added to it, when a clear solution was obtained. It was filtered and the filtrate was added to rectified spirit acidified with HCl (500 c. c., 5% HCl) when it was obtained as a white sticky mass. On trituration with absolute alcohol it was obtained as a white powder. Three similar treatments afforded a white powder (ash, 0.64%, mainly Ca^{++}). The powder did not yield acetic acid on alkaline hydrolysis followed by acidification and steam-distillation.

The gum was acidic to litmus and had equiv. 1245. It was found to contain 2.38% methoxyl. It did not reduce Fehling's solution. It gave positive tests for pentosan and yielded mucic acid (m. p. 215° with decomp.) on oxidation with nitric acid, indicating the presence of galactan or galacturonic acid. Tests for methylpentoses and ketoses were negative. The quantitative analysis of the gum for different constituents has been already given above.

Hydrolysis of the Gum by 10% H_2SO_4 .—The purified gum (10 g.) was suspended in 10% H_2SO_4 (100 c. c.) and the mixture was kept overnight. This was necessary, as heating of the suspension caused immediate decomposition of the uronic acid component. After keeping the suspension for 12 to 15 hours, it was heated on a water-bath at 90° and the hydrolysis was followed polarimetrically as well as by estimating the reducing power of the hydrolysate by Bertrand and Mohr's method.

TABLE I

Period (in hours)	0	1	2	3	4	8
$[\alpha]_D^{25}$	could not be observed.	+41°	+67°	+71°	+76°	+76°
Reducing power of the hydrolysate (in terms of glucose)	0	37	72.5	83.3	87	87

The hydrolysate was then neutralised after 8 hours with barium carbonate, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated to a syrup (10 c. c.) under reduced pressure. The syrup was added to absolute alcohol (30 c. c.) when the precipitate of the barium salt of aldobionic acid was obtained. The alcoholic extract was removed from the precipitate of the barium salt (B) and was concentrated to a syrup (A) (6.8 g.).

Examination of the Sugar Syrup (A).—The chromatographic examination of the sugar syrup (A) according to the method of Partridge (*Nature*, 1946, 168, 270) and developed by the improved method of Novellie (*ibid.*, 1950, 166, 745) indicated the presence of galactose and arabinose. They were identified by running authentic samples side by

side. The sugar syrup became solid on keeping. It was refluxed with dry methanol (20 c. c.). On cooling, the alcoholic extract was removed and the residue was re-extracted with dry methyl alcohol. The alcoholic extracts were combined and were concentrated to a thin syrup, which yielded crystalline arabinose on keeping in a refrigerator for a couple of days. It was recrystallised according to the method of Anderson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 3172), when pure arabinose was obtained, m. p. 157-58°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +102° (c, 2% in water). Mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen remained unchanged. It afforded diphenylhydrazone, m. p. and mixed m. p., 201°. The chromatographic examination of the residue indicated that the residue was galactose containing traces of arabinose. It was crystallised by following the procedure adopted by Klaas and Sands (*ibid.*, 1929, **51**, 3441), when pure crystalline galactose was obtained, m. p. 164-65°, mixed m. p. with authentic galactose 164-65°; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +80° (c, 2% in water). It gave α -methylphenylhydrazone, m. p. and mixed m. p. 186°.

The Barium Salt (B).—The gummy residue (B) was extracted with 90% ethanol till it was chromatographically pure, yield 1.2 g. It contained Ba, 17.55%; OMe, 7.25; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +10° (c, 2% in water). Further hydrolysis of this acid by 10% H₂SO₄ was tried, when the hydrolysate turned blackish brown. The neutralised hydrolysate on chromatographic examination indicated the presence of galactose. The uronic acid could not be isolated from the hydrolysate. Attempts were made to oxidise the uronic acid and thus to obtain mucic acid or potassium acid saccharate according to the method of Goebel and Heidelberger (*loc. cit.*), but mucic acid or the acid saccharate could not be isolated.

Methanolysis of the Barium Salt of Aldobionic Acid.—The barium salt (30 g.) was subjected to methanolysis by suspending it in 7% anhydrous methanolic hydrogen chloride and heating it under reflux. The methanolysis was followed polarimetrically, +46°.4 (0 hr.); +90°.88 (8 hrs.); 92°.8 (16 hrs.); +92°.8 (18 hrs.). The solution was then neutralised with silver carbonate, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The syrup, thus obtained, was taken up in acetone (100 c. c.), and anhydrous ether (400 c. c.) was added to it when a precipitate was obtained. It was redissolved in acetone (20 c. c.) and precipitated by ether (80 c. c.). The precipitate on distillation under reduced pressure yielded a viscous liquid, yield 3.2 g. $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, 94°.5 (c, 2% in MeOH); η_{sp}^{20} , 1.4720. [Found: Equiv., 232; OMe, 38.95; C, 46.18; H, 6.78 per cent]. Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2646) records the following constants for methyl ester of 4-methyl methylglucuronoside: equiv., 240; OMe, 38.4%; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +50° (c, 2.7% in methanol); η_{sp}^{20} , 1.4715 to 1.4737; C₈H₁₆O₇ requires C, 46.24; H, 6.78; OMe, 39.4 per cent; equiv., 236. This indicated that the ester obtained above might be the methyl ester of 4-methyl methylglucuronoside. This was confirmed by preparing its amide by treating the ester with methyl alcoholic ammonia. Crystallisation of the amide from ethanol containing a few drops of water yielded thick white plates, m. p. 234°; $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +152° (c, 1% in water). (Found: C, 43.49; H, 6.97; OMe, 29.0. Calc. for C₈H₁₆O₈N: C, 43.50; H, 6.85; OMe, 28.05 per cent). Smith (*loc. cit.*) reported m. p. of the amide of 4-methyl methyl- α -D-glucuronoside as 235°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$, +150° (c, 1% in water).